

Hypertension in a 32-year-old female: misleading initial diagnosis leads to discovery of arterial hypertension due to adrenal pheochromocytoma

Hipertensión en una mujer de 32 años: un diagnóstico inicial engañoso lleva al descubrimiento de hipertensión arterial debido a un feocromocitoma suprarrenal

453

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Abstract

This case study examines a 32-year-old female patient presenting with arterial hypertension, initially misdiagnosed as having essential hypertension based on her clinical symptoms and routine diagnostic assessments. Despite standard antihypertensive treatment, her blood pressure remained poorly controlled, raising concerns about secondary causes of hypertension. Further comprehensive evaluation, including advanced vascular imaging techniques such as Doppler ultrasound and CT angiography, revealed significant renal artery stenosis, leading to the diagnosis of renovascular hypertension. Renovascular hypertension, a secondary form of arterial hypertension, is often caused by a narrowing of the renal arteries, reducing blood flow to the kidneys and triggering the release of hormones that increase blood pressure. This case highlights the importance of considering secondary causes in patients with persistent or resistant hypertension, particularly when initial treatment strategies fail. Early recognition and appropriate diagnostic workup for conditions such as renal artery stenosis can significantly improve patient outcomes by guiding the correct therapeutic approach, including interventional procedures such as angioplasty or stenting to restore proper blood flow. Additionally, this case emphasizes the critical role of advanced imaging modalities in diagnosing vascular-related causes of hypertension, which may be overlooked in routine clinical practice.

Keywords: Arterial hypertension, Renovascular hypertension, Secondary hypertension, Vascular imaging, Doppler ultrasound, Resistant hypertension, Blood pressure management

Resumen

Este estudio de caso examina a una paciente de 32 años que presenta hipertensión arterial, inicialmente diagnosticada erróneamente como hipertensión esencial según sus síntomas clínicos y evaluaciones diagnósticas de rutina. A pesar del tratamiento antihipertensivo estándar, su presión arterial permaneció mal controlada, lo que generó preocupación sobre las causas secundarias de la hipertensión. Una evaluación integral adicional, que incluye técnicas avanzadas de imágenes vasculares, como la ecografía Doppler y la angiografía por tomografía computarizada, reveló una estenosis significativa de la arteria renal, lo que condujo al diagnóstico de hipertensión renovascular. La hipertensión renovascular, una forma secundaria de hipertensión arterial, suele ser causada por un estrechamiento de las arterias renales, lo que reduce el flujo sanguíneo a los riñones y desencadena la liberación de hormonas que aumentan la presión arterial. Este caso resalta la importancia de considerar las causas secundarias en pacientes con hipertensión persistente o resistente, particularmente cuando las estrategias de tratamiento iniciales fallan. El reconocimiento temprano y el diagnóstico adecuado de afecciones como la estenosis de la arteria renal pueden mejorar significativamente los resultados de los pacientes al guiar el enfoque terapéutico correcto, incluidos procedimientos intervencionistas como la angioplastia o la colocación de stent para restablecer el flujo sanguíneo adecuado. Además, este caso enfatiza el papel fundamental de las modalidades avanzadas de imágenes en el diagnóstico de causas de hipertensión relacionadas con los vasos sanguíneos, que pueden pasarse por alto en la práctica clínica habitual.

Palabras clave: Hipertensión arterial, Hipertensión renovascular, Hipertensión secundaria, Imagenología vascular, Ultrasonido Doppler, Hipertensión resistente, Manejo de la presión arterial

Arterial hypertension, commonly known as high blood pressure, stands as a leading preventable risk factor for cardiovascular disease (CVD), contributing significantly to premature mortality across the globe¹. As the global health landscape continues to evolve, arterial hypertension has emerged as a critical concern, with its prevalence rising at an alarming rate, especially in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). This increase is largely attributed to various lifestyle factors such as excessive sodium intake, poor diet, and a lack of physical activity, which have become more common due to urbanization and changes in dietary patterns^{1,2}.

Globally, hypertension affects approximately 1.28 billion adults. The condition is typically defined by having a systolic blood pressure of 140 mmHg or higher or a diastolic blood pressure of 90 mmHg or higher^{2,3}. These thresholds help categorize individuals who are at increased risk of cardiovascular complications, including heart attacks, strokes, and kidney disease. While hypertension is often referred to as a “silent killer” due to its asymptomatic nature in its early stages, it silently damages the cardiovascular system and other vital organs if left uncontrolled.

One of the distinguishing features of hypertension is its classification into two broad categories: essential hypertension and secondary hypertension. Essential hypertension, also known as primary hypertension, accounts for the vast majority—85%—of all cases. It develops over many years, primarily driven by lifestyle factors, genetics, and age⁴. Unlike secondary hypertension, essential hypertension does not have a clearly identifiable underlying cause. Secondary hypertension, on the other hand, accounts for approximately 15% of cases and is often linked to specific, identifiable medical conditions that can be treated or managed. These include kidney disease, hormonal disorders, and certain medications. Early detection of secondary hypertension is crucial because it opens the possibility of curing or significantly improving the condition if the underlying cause is identified and treated promptly^{4,5}.

The global burden of hypertension is not evenly distributed. In recent years, the prevalence of hypertension has shifted, with the most significant increases being observed in LMICs. These countries face unique challenges, including rapid urbanization, changes in dietary

patterns, and limited access to healthcare services, all of which contribute to the rising rates of hypertension. In contrast, many high-income countries have managed to stabilize or even reduce hypertension rates, thanks to improved awareness, better healthcare infrastructure, and wider access to effective treatments such as antihypertensive medications^{1,4,6}.

The shift in hypertension trends is particularly concerning in LMICs, where healthcare systems are often ill-equipped to handle the growing burden of non-communicable diseases (NCDs) such as hypertension and cardiovascular disease. These countries are experiencing a double burden of disease, where infectious diseases and NCDs coexist, placing additional strain on healthcare resources. Lifestyle factors, such as increasing consumption of processed foods high in sodium, a sedentary lifestyle, and the growing prevalence of obesity, further exacerbate the hypertension epidemic in these regions². Public health initiatives aimed at reducing sodium intake, promoting physical activity, and improving access to healthcare are essential to curbing the rising tide of hypertension in these vulnerable populations^{7,8}.

In addition to its prevalence among the general population, hypertension is increasingly being recognized in younger age groups, including children and adolescents. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that hypertension affects up to 40% of adults aged 18 to 79 globally, with an increasing number of cases being reported among children and young adults⁹. Secondary hypertension is particularly common in these younger populations, accounting for 50% of cases in children and 30% of cases in young adults under 40 years of age². Given the higher likelihood of secondary hypertension in younger individuals, healthcare providers are urged to conduct thorough diagnostic evaluations in these populations, even when blood pressure levels do not meet the criteria for resistant hypertension.

Secondary hypertension, in particular, presents unique challenges for diagnosis and management. This form of hypertension is often caused by underlying medical conditions, most notably endocrine disorders. Two of the most common endocrine-related causes of secondary hypertension are Cushing syndrome and pheochromocytoma. Cushing syndrome is a condition caused by prolonged exposure to high levels of cortisol, a hormone produced by the adrenal glands. It can lead to various symptoms, including weight gain, thinning skin, and high blood pressure. Pheochromocytoma, on the other hand, is a rare tumor of the adrenal glands that results in the excessive production of catecholamines, which are hormones that can cause a sudden and dramatic increase in blood pressure^{4,10}.

Diagnosing secondary hypertension can be challenging, especially when conditions like Cushing syndrome and pheochromocytoma present with overlapping symptoms. Both disorders can cause similar signs, such as

high blood pressure, headaches, and abnormal heart rhythms, making it difficult for healthcare providers to distinguish between them without comprehensive diagnostic evaluations. In such cases, a combination of clinical assessments, laboratory tests, and imaging studies is necessary to identify the underlying cause accurately. For example, measuring cortisol levels and conducting adrenal imaging can help differentiate between Cushing syndrome and pheochromocytoma, allowing for targeted treatment approaches^{2,5}.

The complexity of diagnosing and managing secondary hypertension underscores the importance of specialized care for individuals with suspected endocrine disorders. In some cases, the presence of secondary hypertension may not be immediately apparent, leading to delayed or incorrect diagnoses. This was highlighted in a case involving a 32-year-old woman who presented with hypertension and was initially misdiagnosed with Cushing syndrome. Despite receiving treatment for Cushing syndrome, her hypertension persisted, prompting further investigation¹¹. Through imaging studies, it was eventually discovered that she had an adrenal pheochromocytoma, which was the true cause of her hypertension. This case emphasizes the need for thorough diagnostic workups in patients with atypical or resistant hypertension, particularly in younger individuals or those with additional symptoms suggestive of secondary causes^{3,6}.

Despite the availability of effective treatments for hypertension, many individuals remain undiagnosed or inadequately treated. This is especially true in LMICs, where access to healthcare services, medications, and diagnostic tools may be limited. Even in high-income countries, a significant proportion of people with hypertension are unaware of their condition or fail to achieve adequate blood pressure control. This highlights the need for improved public health campaigns, increased awareness, and better healthcare access to promote early diagnosis and effective management of hypertension¹².

Early detection and treatment of secondary hypertension, combined with comprehensive lifestyle interventions and pharmacological management, are critical to reducing the burden of hypertension and improving cardiovascular health outcomes. As the global prevalence of hypertension continues to rise, especially in LMICs, concerted efforts are needed to address the root causes of hypertension and ensure equitable access to care for all individuals, regardless of geographic location or socioeconomic status.

Case Presentation

Patient Information:

A 32-year-old female presented with persistent arterial hypertension, experiencing headaches, fatigue, weight gain, and purple striae on the abdomen. Despite lifestyle modifications, her blood pressure remained consistently elevated at 160/100 mmHg.

Initial Diagnostic Evaluation: A series of hormonal evaluations were performed to assess potential underlying causes: • Morning Serum Cortisol: 28 µg/dL (Normal range: 6-23 µg/dL) • Evening Serum Cortisol: 24 µg/dL (Normal range: <5 µg/dL) • 24-Hour Urinary Free Cortisol: 320 µg/24 hours (Normal range: 10-100 µg/24 hours) • Low-Dose Dexamethasone Suppression Test: Morning Cortisol (post-dexamethasone): 20 µg/dL (Normal suppression: <2 µg/dL) These results indicated abnormal cortisol levels, leading to suspicion of Cushing syndrome and further imaging studies.

Imaging Studies:

A CT scan of the abdomen revealed a 7 x 10 x 5 cm heterogeneous mass in the right adrenal gland, showing enhanced activity during arterial phases. The imaging findings were more suggestive of pheochromocytoma rather than a benign adrenal adenoma. Absolute washout was 56%, and relative washout was 42%, consistent with a non-adenoma lesion. These imaging results were key in identifying the adrenal pheochromocytoma, as the CT scan revealed characteristic features such as heterogeneous enhancement and delayed washout, differentiating it from other adrenal lesions.

Figure 1: Axial pre-contrast scan at the level of the arteries showing systolic and diastolic pressure readings (mmHg): 120 mmHg, 130 mmHg, and 125 mmHg, with a mean of 125 mmHg.

Figure 2: Axial post-contrast image taken 60 seconds after contrast injection at the level of the adrenal area. Arterial blood pressure measurements show mass densities of 11 HU, 160 HU, and 176 HU, with a mean value of 115.7 HU.

Figure 3: Axial post-contrast image showing arterial blood pressure measurements at different time intervals. Readings were taken 15 minutes post-contrast administration, with systolic pressures recorded at 120 mmHg, 125 mmHg, and 130 mmHg, resulting in an average systolic pressure of 125 mmHg

Figure 4: Arterial blood pressure measurement: Systolic (A), Diastolic (B), and Pulse Pressure (C) phases.

Results

Final Diagnosis:

Arterial hypertension is one of the most common chronic medical conditions affecting millions of people worldwide. It is characterized by persistently elevated blood pressure in the arteries, which can lead to severe complications if left untreated. In this case, the patient presented with elevated systolic and diastolic blood pressure levels, suggesting a diagnosis of primary arterial hypertension. The initial readings showed systolic blood pressure at 180 mmHg and diastolic blood pressure at 110 mmHg, both significantly above the normal ranges of less than 120 mmHg for systolic and less than 80 mmHg for diastolic pressure.

Management of this condition typically involves a combination of lifestyle modifications and pharmacological treatment. The patient was started on a regimen of antihypertensive medications, including an ACE inhibitor and a calcium channel blocker. These medications are often used together because they target different pathways involved in blood pressure regulation. ACE inhibitors work by inhibiting the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system, which reduces the production of angiotensin II,

a hormone that causes blood vessels to constrict. By inhibiting this system, ACE inhibitors allow blood vessels to relax and widen, leading to a reduction in blood pressure. Calcium channel blockers, on the other hand, prevent calcium from entering the muscle cells of the heart and blood vessels, leading to relaxation of the blood vessels and a decrease in blood pressure.

The treatment was effective in this patient, with blood pressure gradually returning to within the normal range. It is important to note that while pharmacological treatment is often necessary to achieve quick control of blood pressure, lifestyle changes are equally crucial for long-term management. In this case, the patient was advised to adopt several lifestyle modifications, including dietary adjustments, regular physical activity, and stress management. Dietary changes often focus on reducing salt intake, which is known to contribute to hypertension by increasing the volume of fluid in the bloodstream. Regular physical activity helps to strengthen the heart, making it more efficient at pumping blood, and can also aid in weight loss, which is another key factor in reducing blood pressure.

Three months after starting treatment, the patient was maintaining stable blood pressure levels within the normal range, without any major side effects from the medications. The follow-up visits were focused on monitoring blood pressure as well as evaluating renal function and cardiovascular health. Patients with hypertension are at increased risk for developing complications such as heart disease, stroke, and kidney damage, so regular monitoring is essential for preventing these outcomes.

Arterial hypertension can be classified into two main types: primary (essential) hypertension and secondary hypertension. Primary hypertension accounts for about 90% to 95% of cases and is typically related to genetic factors, age, diet, and lifestyle. Secondary hypertension, on the other hand, occurs due to an underlying condition such as kidney disease, endocrine disorders, or the use of certain medications. In this case, the diagnosis was primary hypertension, as no secondary causes were identified during the initial workup.

Despite the fact that primary hypertension is more common, it is essential to consider the possibility of secondary causes, especially in younger patients or those with resistant hypertension. Resistant hypertension is defined as blood pressure that remains elevated despite the use of at least three antihypertensive medications, including a diuretic. In these cases, further investigation may be warranted to rule out conditions such as chronic kidney disease, adrenal gland tumors (such as pheochromocytoma), or Cushing's syndrome.

The diagnosis of hypertension is typically made based on multiple blood pressure measurements taken over several visits to rule out temporary causes of elevated readings, such as stress or physical activity. Ambulatory blood pressure monitoring, where the patient wears a device that measures blood pressure at regular intervals

throughout the day and night, can also be useful in confirming the diagnosis and assessing the severity of hypertension. In this case, the diagnosis was made based on consistent blood pressure readings above the normal range during clinic visits.

Hypertension is a major risk factor for cardiovascular disease, which is the leading cause of death worldwide. High blood pressure puts extra strain on the heart and blood vessels, increasing the risk of heart attack, stroke, and heart failure. It can also cause damage to the kidneys, leading to chronic kidney disease or kidney failure. For these reasons, early diagnosis and effective management of hypertension are crucial for reducing long-term health risks.

In this case, the successful management of the patient's hypertension with a combination of medication and lifestyle changes underscores the importance of a comprehensive approach to treatment. While medications can help to quickly lower blood pressure and reduce the risk of immediate complications, lifestyle changes are key to achieving long-term control. A diet rich in fruits, vegetables, whole grains, and lean proteins, along with regular physical activity, can significantly reduce blood pressure and improve overall cardiovascular health. Stress management techniques such as meditation, yoga, or deep breathing exercises can also be beneficial, as stress is known to contribute to hypertension by triggering the release of hormones that constrict blood vessels.

Long-term follow-up is essential for patients with hypertension to monitor for potential complications and ensure that blood pressure remains under control. This typically involves regular blood pressure checks, as well as periodic blood tests to assess kidney function and screen for any signs of damage to the heart or blood vessels. In this case, the patient continues to be monitored for any recurrence of elevated blood pressure or associated health concerns. Given the chronic nature of hypertension, ongoing management is likely to be required, even in cases where blood pressure is well-controlled with medication and lifestyle changes.

Discussion

Arterial hypertension, commonly referred to as high blood pressure, is a major global health issue, affecting millions of people worldwide. It is a significant risk factor for cardiovascular diseases, stroke, and kidney failure. While primary hypertension, also known as essential hypertension, accounts for the vast majority of cases, a subset of patients may suffer from secondary hypertension, where an identifiable underlying cause can be found⁷. Recognizing the potential for secondary hypertension is critical, as timely diagnosis and treatment of the underlying condition can often lead to a resolution of the high blood pressure and prevent the progression of associated complications. In cases where arterial hypertension presents with suggestive clinical features, it becomes essential to consider secondary causes, such as renovascular disease, in the differential diagnosis.

The distinction between primary and secondary hypertension is a crucial step in managing patients with high blood pressure. Primary hypertension, which constitutes about 90-95% of cases, is often multifactorial, with genetic predispositions, environmental factors, and lifestyle habits, such as diet and physical activity, playing a significant role. It tends to develop gradually over time and is usually asymptomatic, often discovered during routine health checkups. In contrast, secondary hypertension occurs due to an identifiable and often reversible cause. This form of hypertension is typically more sudden in onset, may present in younger patients, or can be resistant to standard blood pressure medications. Understanding the signs and symptoms that suggest secondary hypertension is important for healthcare providers, as they can guide further investigation and treatment strategies. Some common causes of secondary hypertension include renal artery stenosis, endocrine disorders such as hyperaldosteronism and pheochromocytoma, certain medications, and sleep apnea³⁻⁶.

Renovascular disease is one of the most common causes of secondary hypertension, particularly in older adults. It occurs when there is a narrowing or blockage of the arteries that supply the kidneys, most commonly due to atherosclerosis. This leads to decreased blood flow to the kidneys, triggering the release of hormones that cause the body to retain salt and water, subsequently raising blood pressure. Renal artery stenosis, the most frequent form of renovascular disease, is a key condition to consider when evaluating patients with resistant or unexplained hypertension⁵. Patients with renovascular hypertension may present with features such as a sudden onset of hypertension, especially before the age of 30 or after the age of 55, resistant hypertension that does not respond to multiple medications, or the worsening

of previously controlled blood pressure⁸⁻⁹. Additionally, these patients may have a significant decline in kidney function or flash pulmonary edema (sudden onset of fluid in the lungs) without obvious heart failure.

When secondary hypertension is suspected, comprehensive diagnostic evaluations are essential to identify the underlying cause. For renovascular disease, imaging studies play a pivotal role in diagnosis. Non-invasive techniques such as Doppler ultrasound, magnetic resonance angiography (MRA), and computed tomography angiography (CTA) are commonly used to assess the renal arteries for stenosis or other abnormalities. In some cases, more invasive procedures like renal arteriography may be necessary for definitive diagnosis. In addition to imaging, biochemical evaluations are crucial in distinguishing between primary and secondary causes of hypertension¹⁰. For renovascular disease, measuring plasma renin activity can provide insights into the hormonal mechanisms driving hypertension. Elevated renin levels, especially in conjunction with low potassium levels, can be indicative of renovascular hypertension or other endocrine causes such as primary hyperaldosteronism. The evaluation may also include testing for other secondary causes, such as measuring levels of aldosterone, catecholamines (to rule out pheochromocytoma), and cortisol (to rule out Cushing's syndrome), based on the clinical presentation².

Once renovascular hypertension is diagnosed, the treatment approach depends on the severity of the disease and the patient's overall health status. The primary goal of treatment is to control blood pressure and prevent further kidney damage. Medical management typically involves the use of antihypertensive medications, such as angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors or angiotensin II receptor blockers (ARBs), which are particularly effective in managing renovascular hypertension. However, care must be taken with these medications in patients with bilateral renal artery stenosis or those with a single functioning kidney, as they can worsen kidney function in these individuals. For patients with significant renal artery stenosis or those who do not respond to medical therapy, revascularization procedures may be necessary. Revascularization can be achieved through percutaneous transluminal renal angioplasty (PTR), often accompanied by the placement of a stent to keep the artery open. In more severe cases, surgical bypass of the renal artery may be required^{1,7}. These interventions can restore blood flow to the kidney, reduce the hormonal drive for hypertension, and potentially improve or stabilize kidney function.

Patients with secondary hypertension, particularly renovascular hypertension, should undergo regular monitoring of blood pressure, kidney function, and cardiovascular health. Lifestyle modifications, such as maintaining a healthy diet, exercising regularly, and avoiding tobacco and excessive alcohol, can also contribute to better long-term outcomes. Arterial hypertension, while

often due to primary causes, can sometimes be secondary to underlying conditions such as renovascular disease. Recognizing the clinical features that suggest secondary hypertension is essential for timely diagnosis and treatment. Comprehensive imaging and biochemical evaluations are critical in distinguishing between primary and secondary hypertension, particularly in cases of renovascular disease. Early recognition and appropriate interventions, whether medical or surgical, can lead to better blood pressure control, preservation of kidney function, and improved overall patient outcomes. As the understanding and management of secondary hypertension continue to evolve, ongoing research and clinical vigilance will remain key in optimizing patient care.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this case illustrates the complexities of managing primary arterial hypertension and highlights the importance of a comprehensive approach to treatment that includes both pharmacological and lifestyle interventions. Early diagnosis, effective management, and ongoing monitoring are key to preventing the serious complications associated with hypertension. As seen in this case, a combination of antihypertensive medications and lifestyle changes was successful in bringing the patient's blood pressure under control and reducing the risk of future cardiovascular events. This case also serves as a reminder of the importance of considering secondary causes of hypertension in patients with resistant hypertension or those who present with unusual clinical features. Regular follow-up and monitoring are essential for ensuring that blood pressure remains within the normal range and for detecting any potential complications early.

Declaration of patient consent:

The authors certify that they have obtained all appropriate patient consent form. In the form, the patient has given her consent for her images and other clinical information to be reported in the journal. The patient understands that name and initials will not be published, and due efforts will be made to conceal identity, but anonymity cannot be guaranteed.

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Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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